

Infrastructural Frameworks: Managing and Publishing Research Research Through the WikiBase Ecosystem

Infrastructural Frameworks Managing and publishing distributed Archaeological Research Data through the Wikibase

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Panel 1: Towards a Common Infrastructural Framework

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The creation of **Linked Open Data** (LOD)
within frameworks like **Wikibase** ...

... has led to an increasing volume of *archaeological big data* stored in **distributed systems** across the **LOD Cloud**.

This growth necessitates strategies to enable **federated SPARQL queries**, facilitating the realisation of **Linked Open Usable Data (LOUD)**.

While the **Arches Management System** offers a robust platform for organising and visualising archaeological data ...

... the **Wikibase Ecosystem**, with its integrated **LOD Knowledge Graph** infrastructures, presents an alternative.

FAIR

FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

Dr. Heidi Seibold, CC BY 4.0, via 10.5281/zenodo.8070860

via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

How does this Wikibase infrastructure work in within broader Knowledge Graph frameworks, in the context of *archaeological big data*?

2007

2008

2009

2010

2011

2017

2018

2019

2020

2023

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Let us see successful applications, and the use of LOD technologies for data analysis and visualisation.

The Wikiverse and Wikibase Instances are part of the LOD Cloud

- ❖ **Items**
 - Label
 - Description
 - Alias
 - Identifier
- ❖ **Statements**
 - Property
 - Value
 - Qualifier
 - Reference

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Wikibase & Wikidata Datamodel

Wikibases in the Wikibase Ecosystem and wikibase.cloud

Croton Numismatics

Hoard analyses of the silver coinage of Croton

Berlin, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin,
1873 Fox, 1825/570, 778 g, 29 mm, 12 h

Hoard analyses of the silver coinage of Croton

Florian Thiery / Stefanie Baars, CC BY 4.0

A lot of findspots show uncertainties and vague information

There is only the information that **the hoard was found on the river Esaro, without specifying exactly where on the river course**. In the literature, there is information that it was found "in Crotona", by which the city rather than the province is meant, otherwise it would have been formulated differently. The urban area of the river course ends shortly after the "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". **The most likely location for the find is along the course of the river between the section just before the motorway and the mouth of the river in the sea**. Since the find was made in 1967, the course of the river at that time probably corresponds fairly closely to the course of the river today. However, both the latter and the presumed find section are conjectures.

Example: Find at Esaro River in 1967

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q67>

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) (Q67)

Am 'Fiume Esaro'.

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio)	Am "Fiume Esaro".	

Statements

instance of	 Archaeological Site
	▼ 0 references
has reference	 P. Attianese (1980)
	▼ 0 references
	 E. A. Arslan (2014)
	▼ 0 references
related to	 http://openstreetmap.org/way/137318585
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#fdubiousMatch
	▼ 0 references
	 http://wikidata.org/entity/Q6681
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#fdubiousMatch
	▼ 0 references

has coordinate

39°57.800′N, 17°6′44.280′E

certainty level Low
method used Georeferencing
acting person Stefanie Baars
source type (detail) Paper
source type (generic) Textual Description
method description set a point based on P. Attianese (1980) and E. A. Arslan (2014) using OSM Way 137318585

certainty description (with language)

There is only the information that the hoard was found on the river Esaro, without specifying exactly where on the river course. In the literature, there is information that it was found "in Crotone", by which the city rather than the province is meant, otherwise it would have been formulated differently. The urban area of the river course ends shortly after the "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". The most likely location for the find is along the course of the river between the section just before the motorway and the mouth of the river in the sea. Since the find was made in 1967, the course of the river at that time probably corresponds fairly closely to the course of the river today. However, both the latter and the presumed find section are conjectures. (English)

Es gibt lediglich die Information, dass der Hortfund am Fluss Esaro gefunden wurde, ohne genaue Angabe, wo am Flusslauf. In der Literatur gibt es die Information, dass er "in Crotone" gefunden wurde, womit eher die Stadt als die Provinz gemeint sein dürfte, da es ansonsten anders formuliert worden wäre. Der städtische Bereich des Flusslaufes endet kurz hinter der "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". Am wahrscheinlichsten ist der Fundort am Flusslauf zwischen dem Abschnitt kurz vor der Autobahn und der Flussmündung im Meer. Da der Fund 1967 getätigt wurde, entspricht der damalige Flussverlauf vermutlich ziemlich genau dem heutigen. Sowohl Letzteres als auch der mutmaßliche Fundabschnitt sind jedoch Vermutungen. (German)

point type Representative Point
precision ±0.000001°
location type Findspot

Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

Irish Holy Wells & Roman Samian Ware

**How to work within Wikidata
with Citizen Scientists?**

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oWvIB>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Example Freshford: St Lachtain's Well in Wikidata

Wikidata
Toberlachtain (Q21840779)

How well illustrated is St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kildare?

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Toberlachtain	How well illustrated is St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kildare?	Toberlachtain
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Russian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

- subclass of: holy well (1 reference)
- subclass of: holy well featuring a cross (4 references)
- subclass of: spring (3 references)
- subclass of: holy well (4 references)
- subclass of: place in Ireland (1 reference)

Image

Named after

- Lachtain Mac Taidh (1 reference)

Country

- Ireland (2 references)

Located in the administrative territorial entity

- County Kildare (1 reference)
- Freshford (1 reference)

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21840779>

Location

52°47'N, 7°22'W

Historical context

- 137: Philip O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kildare II
- 1823: Medical condition treated

External data available at URL

- https://www.celticcross.com/monuments/monuments-well-holy-well/16144/7433/638/679/2471/1644/9/

Identified by source

- Q2184: The Place Names of County Kildare (13 references)
- Historical Environment (Ireland) (1 reference)
- The British Geographical Names (2 references)
- Labels comprising information related to the publication of the County of Kildare collected during the progress of the Ordnance Survey (1823) (1 reference)
- The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory II (25 references)

Identified by source

- 6 Irish First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland (2 references)
- Philip O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kildare in terms of diocesan coverage, location, their practices and economy (1 reference)
- Philip O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kildare II (137 references)
- Notes and Contents of County Kildare by Paris Anderson (23 references)
- Edward Carleton: Theophilus (33,34 references)
- Historical, Social and Pictures Sketches of Freshford (18 references)
- Red Book of Ossory (2 references)

Commons category

- Toberslachten (2 references)

Identifiers

- Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID: KK013-025---- (1 reference)
- OpenStreetMap way ID: 935503837 (0 references)
- Wells-Lakes-Monuments ID: 935503837 (0 references)

Identifiers

- Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID: KK013-025---- (1 reference)
- OpenStreetMap way ID: 935503837 (0 references)

Example Freshford: St Lachtain's Well in Wikidata

Samian Research relational database

Linked Open Data based on CIDOC CRM

publication via archaeology.link

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfagen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Wikidata -> Item Typo [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: Item Label Layer Name: Item_jc

SPARQL Query

```

1 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdtr: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wikibase: <http://wikiba.se/ontology/>
4 PREFIX ps: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/>
5 PREFIX ps: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/statement/>
6 PREFIX ps: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/qualifier/>
7 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
8 PREFIX bd: <http://www.bigdata.com/rdf#>
9
10 #defaultView:Map(["?geo"])
11 # Samian Ware Productioncentres
12 SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geo ?layerLabel ?player WHERE {
13 ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202026;
14 wdt:P261 wd:Q90412636;
15 wdt:P295 ?geo;
16 wdt:P2888 ?samian;
17 wdt:P706 ?player.
18 ?player wdt:P51 wd:Q102201947.
19 SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language ["AUTO_LANGUAGE",en" ] }
20 }

```

Filter Concept Results:

- GeoConcepts (500)
- FeatureCollections
- GeometryC
- Antarctic field camp (wd:Q771007)
- Antarctic research station (wd:Q19662)
- Baha temple (wd:Q136013)
- British overseas territory (wd:Q1005)
- Catholic cathedral (wd:Q421215)
- Central American city (wd:Q1005)
- Central American concresses (wd:Q182656)
- Christian denomination (wd:Q879146)
- Christian school (wd:Q87752)
- Coche (wd:Q2450730)
- Conservatory of departmental relevance ...
- Ecclesiastical organisation immediately ...
- French overseas collectivity (wd:Q719487)
- French ware (wd:Q88933)
- Geodermis barktick (wd:Q1554032)
- Gregorian telescope (wd:Q7423118)
- Hot water (wd:Q147261)
- Mercury crater (wd:Q2833930)
- NADAA Weather Radio station ...
- National Monument of the United States ...
- National Park of the United States ...
- National Reserve (wd:Q897670)
- Nature Wildlife Refuge (wd:Q141666)
- One Earth Ecogroup (wd:Q124231947)
- Pitman eruption (wd:Q15705)
- Protestant church building (wd:Q5642626)
- Roman Catholic metropolitan archdiocese ...
- Scenic Reserve (wd:Q8148569)
- Sekolah Menengah Atas (wd:Q2796936)
- Selatan Menengah Utama (wd:Q2796932)
- Surtseyan eruption (wd:Q1968842)

Geoschritte: Queries | CheckSt | Query | Queryname | Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

via <https://www.wiki/Ba3A>

SPARQL Unicorn

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0. Data via Wikidata, CCO and Samian Research, m-DPPL

The Samian Research LOD / Wikidata Workflow

Wikidata Community, Public Domain, via w.wiki/6HLH

Wikidata Query Service

```

1 # Samian Ware Discovery Sites
2 #defaultView:Map
3 SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geom
4 WHERE
5 {
6   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202066.
7   ?item wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636.
8   ?item wdt:P625 ?geom.
9   ?item wdt:P2888 ?samian.
10  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
11 }
    
```

Wikidata Community, Public Domain, via w.wiki/6HLM

Wikidata Query Service

```

1 # Samian Ware Productioncentres
2 #defaultView:Map
3 SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geom
4 WHERE
5 {
6   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202026.
7   ?item wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636.
8   ?item wdt:P625 ?geom.
9   ?item wdt:P2888 ?samian.
10  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
11 }
    
```

Wikidata Community, Public Domain, via w.wiki/4pDu

Wikidata Query Service

```

1 # Samian Ware kilnRegions
2 #defaultView:Map["hide":["?geom","?samian"]]
3 SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geo ?layer WHERE {
4   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102201947;
5   wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636;
6   wdt:P2888 ?samian;
7   wdt:P3896 ?geo.
8   optional { ?item wdt:P2888 ?layer. }
9   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
10 }
    
```


The Samian Research LOD / Wikidata Entities

Campanian Ignimbrite

Findspots from the CI eruption 40,000 yr b2k

Breislak, Scipione (1748-1826). Voyages physiques et lythologiques dans la Campanie. Paris: Dentu, Imprimeur-libraire, 1801, via https://vulcan.lindahall.org/12_large.shtml

About 40,000 yr b2k ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields.

Evidence of the ash fall from this late Pleistocene volcanic event can be found throughout Central Europe.

These sites are recorded in several publications, e.g. with coordinates or references to cities, regions, caves and archaeological sites.

via https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/Site_collection/index.html

Squirrel Data | CI FSL | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network Nuts?

Site Instances Collection EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/Site_collection

The Site Instances Collection resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Property	Value
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<code>FeatureCollection</code> (gsp:FeatureCollection) [x]
<code>label</code> (rdfs:label)	Site Instances Collection (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>member</code> (rdfs:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▼ 71 values• Acerra Sink (fsl:dc:site_1)• Acqua Fidia (fsl:dc:site_2)• Balta Alba (Romania) (fsl:dc:site_57)• Batanica (fsl:dc:site_104)• Bratul Borcea (Romania) (fsl:dc:site_56)• Capezzano (fsl:dc:site_3)• Casola (fsl:dc:site_4)• Castelcivita Cave (fsl:dc:site_5)• Copecchia (fsl:dc:site_6)

All these sites and information can be published as Linked Open Data

Figure 1. Geographic distribution of the Campanian Ignimbrite deposits, including archaeological and sampling sites mentioned in the paper. Solid squares: CI tephra occurrences and related thickness in cm (in italics if reworked) [modified from *Cornell et al., 1983; Amirkhanov et al., 1993; Cini Castagnoli et al., 1995; Narcisi and Vezzoli, 1999; Fedele et al., 2002; Upton et al., 2002*]. Dotted area in central Italy: distribution of the CI-derived paleosol (CI-PS [*Frezzaotti and Narcisi, 1996*]). Solid triangles: archaeological sites with CI ash layer. Blank triangles: archaeological sites with ash layer attributed to the CI on the basis of cultural-stratigraphic position and ^{14}C dating (*Fedele et al., 2002; Giaccio and Isaia, on file*). Solid circles: selected European Palaeolithic sites within the area potentially affected by the CI air-fall.

Franchthi Cave (Greece) in Fedele et al. (2003)

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Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/cisite_45/index.html

Squirrel Data | © PSL | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Franchthi Cave (Greece)

https://frayzy.vl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_45

The **Franchthi Cave (Greece)** resource is powered by **Static ContentHub** generated using the **SHRDLUing** **Visium QGIS** **Plugin**

Search:

Description:

View/Options:

Property	Value
<code>archaeologicalResourceID</code>	Franchthi Cave is a scientific paper and field on OpenStreetMap (url=http://openstreetmap.org/way/123456789)
<code>authorName</code>	John Doe
<code>authorEmail</code>	john.doe@openstreetmap.org
<code>authorTwitter</code>	@JohnDoe
<code>authorGitHub</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorLinkedIn</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorFacebook</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorInstagram</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorYouTube</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorVimeo</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorSoundCloud</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorDribbble</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorBehance</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorFlickr</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorDeviantArt</code>	JohnDoe
<code>author500px</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorGoodreads</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorLibraryThing</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorAcademia</code>	JohnDoe
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<code>authorOpenStaxOrg98</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorOpenStaxOrg99</code>	JohnDoe
<code>authorOpenStaxOrg100</code>	JohnDoe

Franchthi Cave as Archaeological Site (fsl:cisite_45) in the LOD Cloud

Auel Maar (AU3/4) & Dehner Maar (DE3) sites in Schenk et al. (2024)

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q70>

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools

What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase

New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item **Discussion**

Auel Maar AU3 (Q70)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Auel Maar AU3	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	Geological Site
	0 references
related to	https://kulturb.de/einobjekt.php?id=23391
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatial/CloseMatch
	0 references
has reference	Schenk et al. (2024)
	1 reference
part of	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
	0 references
has spatial type	Maar
	0 references

has coordinate 50°16′57.0″N, 6°35′42.4″E

certainty level	High
certainty description	stated in scientific paper, Schenk et al. (2024), fig. 1
method used	Georeferencing
acting person	Fiona Schenk
method description	site survey
source type (detail)	Paper
source type (generic)	Textual Description
precision	±0.0001°
location type	Findspot
point type	Investigation Place

1 reference

reference URL	https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017
---------------	---

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

Auel AU3 [Q70] in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

Ogham Stones

How to create a Ogham Wikibase Ecosystem?

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.502

4.-6. AD early Medieval “Primitive Irish”

Al-qamar / CC BY-SA 3.0 via Wikimedia Commons

Florian Thierry, CC BY-SA 4.0

Ogham!

The open Ogham data workflow!

CIIC 81

- UCC Cork Stone Corridor: #4
- OSM Node: 11071361392
- Wikidata: Q130529871

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthiergyeo

Änderungssatz #13909380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[AJSSITT]A7O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Use each LOD/ Wikibase-Instance for data it is “famous” for

- *Linked Open Ogham Data*: providing the primary URI
 - <https://t1p.de/3xqti>
- *fuzzy-sl Wikibase*: coordinates and how they are created
 - [P4](#)
- *Wikidata*: data-hub for external identifiers, e.g., OSM, SMRS, LOD
 - [P11693](#), [P4057](#), [P2888](#)
- *Semantic Kompakkt Wikibase*: 3D Model & Annotations
 - [P74](#), [P75](#)
- *FactGrid Wikibase for Historians*: Inscription & Persons & Words
 - [P1219](#), [P33](#), [P256](#)

The Idea: Create LOD and feed domain-specific Wikibase Instances

via <https://www.istor.org/stable/25505959>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL; <https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/6168494>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL;
<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/56702954>

alt_name	Garranes Ringfort
archaeological_site	fortification
fortification_type	ringfort
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	celtic
name	Lisnacaheragh Ringfort

Rath called
Lisheenagreine
ca. 51.81655, -8.76587

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Past: CIIC 81 at the original? findspot in Garranes (Lisheenagreine)

Florian Thery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Today: Looking at the UCC Stone corridor

Main page
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Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q74)

Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork	

Statements

instance of	 Archaeological Site
	▼ 0 references

related to	 http://wikidata.org/entity/Q130529871
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 https://wikibase.semantic-kompakt.de/entity/Q1247
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q1000294
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

related to	 http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081
	related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch
	▼ 0 references

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

certainty level Low

certainty description Gippert/Web, Ogham 81: "According to Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurranes (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurranes" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map

of the rath (in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P. O' R'Yordain's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in JRSAI 10, 1869); Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurranes. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches". CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.!

method used

acting person

source type (generic)

source type (detail)

method description

precision

location type

point type

Georeferencing

Florian Thiery

Textual Description

Paper

found in old documents

±0.0001°

Findspot

Location of a Place as a Concept

has coordinate

51°53'37.3"N, 8°29'32.6"W

certainty level

High

certainty description

on-site survey at exhibition area

method used

on-site survey

acting person

Florian Thiery

source type (detail)

on-site survey (source type)

source type (generic)

on-site survey (source type)

method description

on-site survey at UCC Cork

precision

±0.0001°

location type

Exhibition Site

point type

Exhibition

▼ 0 references

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI
- Cite this page
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q130529871)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

[edit](#)

CIIC 81

[In more languages](#)

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	CIIC 81
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	 ogham stone edit 0 references + add reference
	 Ogham Stone Semantic Concept edit 0 references + add reference
	 archaeological artifact edit 0 references + add reference + add value

Identifiers

FactGrid item ID Q1000294
[0 references](#)

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID CO074-148----
[0 references](#)

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392
[0 references](#)

Wikidata [Q130529871]

Main page
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Wikibase
New item
New property
New schema
List properties
Query service

Tools
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Related changes
Upload file
Special pages
Printable version
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Concept URI

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1247)

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor edit

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	
British English	No label defined	No description defined	

Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL	
		+ add mapping

Statements

instance of Media Item edit

0 references + add reference

+ add value

license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike edit

0 references + add reference

+ add value

has technique Photogrammetry edit

file view

<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Related agents

Rightsowner: [University College Cork \(UCC\)](#)

Data Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Editor: [Florian Thiery](#)

Contact Person: [Florian Thiery](#)

Licence

[Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International \(CC BY-NC-SA 4.0\)](#)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)

Software: [KIRI engine](#)

Equipment: Smartphone

Date: Invalid Date

Related object structure

[Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV](#)

Semantic Kompakkt [Q1247]

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

CnFdI
3D DATA ENRICHMENT

Item Discussion

C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81) (Q1255)

Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81)	Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI

Main page
Recent changes
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New item

Semantic Kompakt [Q1247]

via <https://database.factorid.de/wiki/Item:Q1000294>

Main page
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Browse
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EntiTree genealogies

Project Spaces
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To Do
SPARQL Lab

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Search

Tools

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Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1000294)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

▾ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor
British English	No label defined	No description defined

Statements

Instance of	Ogham Stone	▾ 0 references
-------------	-------------	----------------

Research projects that contributed to this data set	The FactGrid Ogham Project (2024-)	▾ 0 references
---	------------------------------------	----------------

Language	Ogham	▾ 0 references
----------	-------	----------------

Genre classification	Ogham Stone	▾ 0 references
----------------------	-------------	----------------

Script style	Ogham	▾ 0 references
--------------	-------	----------------

inscription	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	▾ 0 references
-------------	----------------------------------	----------------

Persons mentioned	cassittas	▾ 0 references
	Calliti	▾ 0 references

Things mentioned	MAQI	▾ 0 references
	MUCOI	▾ 0 references

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▾ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Calliti (Q1013407)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

▾ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Calliti	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

MAQI (Q1013408)

son

MAQ | MAC | /-M- | MACCI | MAQCI | MACV | MACI

▾ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MAQI	son	MAQ MAC /-M- MACCI MAQCI MACV MACI

MUCOI (Q1013410)

túath, tribe

/-M-... | MACCU | MOCU | MOCOI | MOCO

▾ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MUCOI	túath, tribe	/-M-... MACCU MOCU MOCOI MOCO

FactGrid [Q1000294]

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinking Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFD40bjects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: oghamsite

Filter Concept Results:

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

GeoConcepts (23)

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Klein region (KleinRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite
- Place
- ProductionCentre
- Province
- State
- Townland

<https://t1p.de/v0lgz>

Squirrel Data | Linked Open Ogham | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Linked Ogham

#81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>

The #81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: [input] Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download

Property	Value
disclosedAt (oghamonto:disclosedAt)	254000020 (Info:Q54000020)
exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)	Q10668073 (Info:Q10668073) [d]
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OghamStone (oghamonto:OghamStone) [d] OghamStone_Spatial (oghamonto:OghamStone_Spatial) [d] Resource (oghamonto:Resource) [d] Resource (oghamonto:Resource) [d]
comment (rdf:comment)	Ogham Stone, Ireland (offLang:en) (Info:Q89188)
label (rdf:label)	#81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (offLang:en) (Info:Q89188)

Metadaten

Property	Value
identifier (ocid:identifier)	#81 (offLang:en)
creator (ocid:creator)	0000-0002-3244-9511 (0000-0002-3244-9511) [d]
license (ocid:license)	deed:de (deed:de) [d]
rightsHolder (ocid:rightsHolder)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0000-0002-3244-9511 (0000-0002-3244-9511) [d] 0000-0001-4496-2700 (0000-0001-4496-2700) [d]
isBasedOn (ocid:isBasedOn)	Linked_Open_Ogham_0bjects(Linked_Open_Ogham) [d]#81 (oghamonto:disclosedAt)
wasAttributedTo (ocid:wasAttributedTo)	PythonStoneCIIC (Info:PythonStoneCIIC)
wasDerivedFrom (ocid:wasDerivedFrom)	og_stones_en (og_stones_en) [d]
wasGeneralizedBy (ocid:wasGeneralizedBy)	00000000_activity (Info:00000000_activity)

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NFD40bjects Knowledge Graph SPARQL

geosparql:Feature
sf:MultiPolygon
sf:Polygon
wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

SPARQL endpoint: /api/sparql (see documentation)

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Table Response (196 results)

item	label	geo	county	count
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000031>	'Ballykeogh (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.071111 52.028644)'	'Cork'	11
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020>	'Drumshook (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(7.648056 52.163056)'	'Waterford'	10
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000026>	'Ballinagney (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(10.051111 52.121222)'	'Kerry'	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000149>	'Kilcolgaigh East, Kihillcane (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(9.747222 52.071944)'	'Kerry'	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000170>	'Knockboy (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(7.6 52.111589)'	'Waterford'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000019>	'Ballinaring (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(10.861111 52.761111)'	'Kerry'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000077>	'Coolingarny (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.642778 52.061111)'	'Kerry'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000073>	'Coblinstown / Killen Corna (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.756389 53.031111)'	'Kildare'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000039>	'Ballyhenry (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.608333 53.896111)'	'Kerry'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000138>	'Knockshanree (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.794722 51.868056)'	'Cork'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000216>	'Ballyhenry (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.103056 52.080556)'	'Kerry'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000154>	'Oghamwan (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(5.649222 52.090556)'	'Waterford'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000181>	'Maraigarran (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(8.279444 51.874444)'	'Cork'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000208>	'Buckfield / Laharna (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(9.631667 52.128889)'	'Cork'	8
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000209>	'Bovena More (Ogham Site)'	'POINT(7.874167 51.886667)'	'Cork'	8

for query results: [input] Engl

LOD Resource as “hub-concept” for the N4O Knowledge Graph ...

... to query it e.g. using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper Filter

object of representation file view wikidata id

Limit

[Query source](#)

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tib:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tib:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tib:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16    wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17    wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18    wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21

```

1 result in 513 ms

3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Federating between **Semantic Kompakkt** & **Wikidata**

Federating between *Wikidata* (external IDs), *FactGrid* (related people and inscriptions), and *fuzzy-sl* (coordinates)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL


```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX fsldw: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fg: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT ?label ?wikiq ?factgridq ?fslq ?inscription ?related_personsLabels ?coordinates ?osmnode ?smrid ?uri WHERE {
10 SERVICE <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql> {
11   ?wikiq wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
12   FILTER(?wikiq = wd:Q130529871)
13   ?wikiq rdfs:label ?label.
14   FILTER(LANG(?label) IN("en"))
15   ?wikiq wdt:P8168 ?factgridq;
16   wdt:P11693 ?osmnode;
17   wdt:P4057 ?smrid;
18   wdt:P2888 ?uri.
19 }
20 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
21   fg:Q1000294 fgt:P1219 ?inscription;
22   fgt:P33 ?related_persons;
23   fgt:P1215 ?fslq.
24   ?related_persons rdfs:label ?related_personsLabels.
25   FILTER(LANG(?related_personsLabels) IN("en"))
26 }
27 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> { fsldw:Q74 fsldw:P4 ?coordinates. }
28 }

```

<https://sparql.dblp.org/YKlrP3>

Query results:

2 lines found 11ms in total 11ms for computation 0.0ms for resolving and sending

	?label	?wikiq	?factgridq	?fslq	?inscription	?related_personsLabels	?coordinates	?osmnode	?smrid	?uri
1	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[À]SSITT[À]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	caslittas	Point(-8.49244311 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074- 148----	Y50000081
2	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[À]SSITT[À]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	Calliti	Point(-8.49244311 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074- 148----	Y50000081

Conclusio

Use Wikibase as Infrastructural Framework

How can I help researchers
without knowledge of
SPARQL in using Linked
Open Data in QGIS?

The SPARQL Unicorn Idea

The **SPARQL Unicorn** allows the *execution of Linked Data queries* in (Geo)SPARQL to selected triplestores and geo-enabled SPARQL endpoints and thus prepares the results of the queries in QGIS for the geocommunity.

<https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS>
via 10.5281/zenodo.3786814

What is the SPARQL Unicorn?

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Wikidata --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Item+Label Layer Name: holy_wells

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?img ?geo ?osm ?namedafterLabel WHERE {
2   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q1371047, wd:Q12644332.
3   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img. }
4   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }
5   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P11693 ?osm. }
6   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P138 ?namedafter. }
7   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
8 }

```


<https://w.wiki/BD2C>

Gespeicherte Queries: ChristSch Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen Language for query results: English (en)

GeoConcepts (500) FeatureCollections GeometryCc

- Antarctic field camp (wd:Q4771007)
- Antarctic research station (wd:Q749622)
- Bahá'í temple (wd:Q1568313)
- British overseas territories (wd:Q46395)
- Catholic cathedral (wd:Q56242215)
- Centaur (wd:Q761888)
- Chondrocladia concrescens (wd:Q1828566)
- Christian denomination (wd:Q879146)
- Christian school (wd:Q867738)
- Coche (wd:Q5403750)
- Conservatory of departmental relevance ...
- Ecclesiastical circumscription immediately ...
- French overseas collectivity (wd:Q719487)
- French wine (wd:Q630531)
- Gendarmierie barracks (wd:Q83554028)
- Gregorian telescope (wd:Q742318)
- Mars crater (wd:Q1475691)
- Mercury crater (wd:Q76833930)
- NOAA Weather Radio station ...
- National Monument of the United States ...
- National Park of the United States ...
- National Reserve (wd:Q6978070)
- National Wildlife Refuge (wd:Q1410668)
- One Earth Ecoregion (wd:Q124221947)
- Plinian eruption (wd:Q747501)
- Protestant church building (wd:Q56242063)
- Roman Catholic metropolitan archdiocese ...
- S-42 (wd:Q1887138)
- Scenic Reserve (wd:Q63248569)
- Sekolah Menengah Atas (wd:Q97598588)
- Sekolah Menengah Pertama (wd:Q97500812)
- Surtseyan eruption (wd:Q1060842)

Use the Unicorn to query Wikibase Instances, such as Wikidata ...

unicorn_holy_wells — Objekte gesamt237, gefiltert: 237, gewählt: 0					
	id	img	itemLabel	namedafterLabel	osm
109	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126923120	NULL	Kilmog Holy Well	friar	NULL
110	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126919273	NULL	Friar's Well	friar	NULL
111	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126491170	NULL	Q126491170	head	NULL
112	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454486	NULL	Well of the head	head	8515246136
113	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454486	NULL	Well of the head	headache	8515246136
114	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126655791	NULL	Caereachth Well	herd	NULL
115	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126472309	NULL	Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	NULL
116	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126374490	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	11942593399
117	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126438084	NULL	Holy Trinity Well	Holy Trinity	8517739108
118	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126486274	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	John's Well	John the Baptist	8539018118
119	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126474774	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St John's Well	John the Baptist	8567014803
120	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126456561	NULL	St. John's Well	John the Baptist	653502216
121	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126472933	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St. James's Well	Kings River	8522332218
122	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St. Lachtain's Well (Toberlachtain)	Lachtin mac Tarbin	NULL
123	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q127049193	NULL	Saint Laurence's Well	Lawrence of Rome	NULL
124	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454422	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St Leonard's Well	Leonard of Noblac	7412516778
125	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126949808	NULL	Loughman's Well	Loughman	NULL
126	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q122303936	NULL	Saint Luke's Well	Luke	8526425065
127	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126478503	NULL	St. Mocuille's Well	Mac Cuill	8522349432
128	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126454603	http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/	St. Mogue's Well	Máedóc of Ferns	7995685476
129	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126485951	NULL	St. Margaret's Well	Margaret the Virgin	8515639045
130	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126476522	NULL	St. Martin's Well	Martin of Tours	8490582674
131	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126880179	NULL	St. Mary's Well	Mary	NULL
132	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126646306	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
133	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126645328	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
134	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126888828	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
135	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126617074	NULL	Our Lady's Well	Mary	NULL
136	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126499565	NULL	Tobar Muire	Mary	11973631439
137	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126479390	NULL	Lady's Well	Mary	NULL

... to do some research in QGIS!

Infrastructural Frameworks: Managing and Published Research Research Through the WikiBase Ecosystem

Finis! Grazie!

Questions?

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